

IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS

Shovkieva Shohida Bobosher Kizi

Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6628431>

English language is an international medium of communication. People use English as a second language to interact and communicate on a daily basis. The English language is a key factor in gaining access to many things. Be it in your career or in terms of knowledge, English language is universally acceptable. In fact, it majorly dominates other languages because of its power of communication. The English language is not as difficult as it is perceived to be. Anyone can learn the language starting with basics. You can gain a lot of information if you know the language well. You need to learn to slow down when you speak. Always think before you speak if you are a beginner. This will help you to speak more clearly. Always select your words properly as it is an important part of communication. For developing active communication skills, it's important to learn sentences and not only words. The more you use bigger sentences, the better it is for your communication skills. Another aspect of communication is developing your listening skills. When you talk to someone in English, always listen and then speak. Listen to what others are saying. Pay attention to details to understand sentences. Communication is a two-way process and it's the same with the English language. Always show interest in other people's opinion when they speak. The three important keys to developing communication skills are learning, speaking and practicing. Learning English is easy and speaking the language will help you open up to the language in a better way. Practice is the key to pick up the language, speak as much as you can. If you are well versed with the English language, then it can actively help you to learn about new things. English language communication increases your chances of earning better as every job skills require English communication. It gives you the power to do things your way. As it's one of the most influential languages, it's great to tool to understand.

You can brace yourself with modern day knowledge with the use of English. You can innovate in a better way with active communication. From creation to implementation, you can do much with the power of English language communication. English language communication can help you make many friends throughout the world. The English language helps you to understand other languages. English is a hybrid mix of languages such as Roman, Vikings, French, and Latin. The English language is truly flexible so it is effective to communicate in this language. You have so many different ways to explain a

single concept. It has a wide range of vocabulary and words. It enhances your reading and writing skills. You can read books or simply write with the power of the language. Communicating in English helps you to gain wisdom and that is the main advantage of the language.

English is popular and perhaps the most effective language for international communication. It is the official language of 53 countries and millions of people across the globe speak English. It lets you communicate easily even while you travel. As English is spoken in almost all the countries, it helps you get rid of the language barrier. English enables you to communicate easily with all the fellow global citizens of the world. When your communication is free, you can actively get access to many things. Today, English is a dominant business language so it is must to know English for bright career prospects. English is a language that is used for the global workforce. In fact, cross-border work communication is mostly conducted in the English language. Most international companies expect their employees to talk in English. Communicating in English is crucial for business and professional needs. English language communication opens the doors for entertainment for you. You can read top-selling books; you can hear the top rated music and watch great movies. If you speak and communicate in English, you will not have to use a translator or depend on subtitles for understanding things. This makes things much easier for you.

To conclude , English language communication increases your confidence level. You can learn the language through different mediums like books, podcasts, and internet. You can also take up an English-speaking course to develop your communication skills. Communicating in English is indispensable in today's times, so develop your skills to excel in life.

Used literature.

1. Ahmad, R. S. The Importance of English Communication Skills. International Journal of Applied Research (2016).
2. Barkley. E. Collaborative Learning techniques. United States of America: John Willey & Sons, Inc. Brown H. Douglas. Principle of Language and Teaching. USA: Prentice-hall, 2007.
3. Brown H. Douglas. Language Assessment: Principles and Classroom Practices. San Francisco State University, 2004.
4. Bruce Tillit, Marry Newton Bruder. Speaking Naturally: Communication Skill in American English. Cambridge University Press, 1999.
5. Bygate, M. Language Teaching Speaking. Oxford University Press. Byrne, Teaching Oral English, New Jersey: Longman Group Ltd

